
THE EMOTIONAL COREGULATION SCALE: A SELF-REPORT MEASURE OF EMOTIONAL CONTAGION AND COUNTER-REGULATION IN CLOSE RELATIONSHIPS

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ABSTRACT

This study introduces and validates a self-report measure of emotional coregulation, conceptualized as two interconnected processes: *emotional contagion*, reflecting the sharing of with a partner, and *counter-regulation*, reflecting balancing a partner's intense emotions with soothing responses. Items were designed to capture these processes across positive and negative emotions and were evaluated in two online samples (round 1: $n = 120$; round 2: $n = 119$). Analyses of item performance, internal consistency, confirmatory factor analysis, and discriminant validity supported reliable one-factor solutions for each subscale. Evidence from discriminant validity testing further indicated that emotional contagion and counter-regulation are related but distinct processes. By capturing these dynamics in self-report form, the scale makes it possible to assess the subjective experience of emotional coregulation in relationships, opening new opportunities for research on interpersonal emotion regulation and relational well-being.

1 Introduction

The ability to regulate emotions is central to psychological health, as it allows individuals to recover from distress and sustain well-being [Gross, 2015]. Traditionally, emotion regulation has been studied as an internal process, yet a growing body of work shows that it is also inherently social. People turn to others to help manage their feelings, and these interactions shape emotional outcomes in everyday life [Rimé, 2007, Zaki and Williams, 2013]. This broader category of interpersonal emotion regulation includes behaviors such as seeking comfort, providing reassurance, and co-constructing emotional meaning. Within this framework lies emotional coregulation, a more dynamic and reciprocal process where two individuals form a coupled emotional system that fluctuates and stabilizes over time [Butler and Randall, 2013, Koole and Tschacher, 2016]. Coregulation involves not only the sharing of emotions, often referred to as emotional contagion, but also counter-regulation, in which one partner helps dampen or balance the other's emotions to maintain a stable equilibrium.

Theoretical models describe emotional coregulation as a system of mutual feedback loops. Butler and Randall [2013] characterize it as a morphostatic process, where partners' emotional states are linked and oscillate around a shared balance point. Contagion reflects a tendency for partners to converge in affective states, while counter-regulation

reflects processes that restore equilibrium when emotions become too intense. Together, these dynamics distinguish coregulation from one-sided support, since both partners influence the trajectory of their shared emotional climate.

Empirical evidence supports the existence of these processes in close adult relationships. Daily diary and observational studies show that partners' emotions often covary, indicating patterns of contagion. For instance, spouses' moods tend to align across the day, with stronger convergence for negative emotions than for positive ones [Saxbe and Repetti, 2010]. Reunion studies similarly show that one partner's affective shifts are mirrored by the other, particularly in couples with greater interpersonal insecurity [Schoebi, 2008]. Evidence of counter-regulation, while less studied, appears in contexts where one partner actively attenuates the other's distress. Coan and colleagues [2006] demonstrated that spousal handholding reduced neural threat responses, suggesting that partners can down-regulate one another's emotional reactivity. Such findings, though correlational, converge on the idea that couples form interconnected emotional systems in which both contagion and counter-regulation shape shared affective trajectories. Beyond behavior, converging physiological evidence—spanning neural hyperscanning, autonomic indices (e.g., RSA, heart rate), and hormonal measures—supports emotional coregulation by showing coordinated partner activity and attenuated threat responding [Bornstein and Esposito, 2023, Helm et al., 2014, Zhou et al., 2024, Wieder and Wiltshire, 2020].

Not all couples coregulate in the same way. Individual differences such as attachment style and relationship quality appear to moderate these dynamics. Anxiously attached partners tend to show heightened contagion, often becoming more entangled in a partner's distress, while avoidant partners disengage from emotional exchanges, weakening linkage [Butner et al., 2007]. Relationship satisfaction also shapes patterns, with couples in higher-quality relationships displaying stronger mutual soothing [Saxbe and Repetti, 2010]. These findings highlight that coregulation is not uniform, but shaped by relational context and individual tendencies.

Despite theoretical and empirical advances, measurement remains a critical gap. Existing instruments capture related constructs but do not address coregulation directly. The Emotional Contagion Scale measures individual susceptibility to catching others' emotions [Doherty, 1997, Marx et al., 2024], while the Interpersonal Emotion Regulation Questionnaire (IERQ) assesses how people enlist others to regulate their own emotions [Hofmann et al., 2016]. Yet these measures focus on one-sided processes rather than the reciprocal loops of contagion and counter-regulation. Researchers studying coregulation have therefore relied on physiological synchrony [Helm et al., 2014, Bornstein and Esposito, 2023, Zhou et al., 2024], behavioral coding, or separate partner reports, but no validated self-report tool exists to capture individuals' subjective experiences of coregulation in close relationships.

In sum, theory and empirical work converge on the view that emotional coregulation is a defining feature of close relationships. Partners not only share each other's emotions through contagion, but also stabilize one another through counter-regulation. These processes are sensitive to relationship context, with evidence suggesting that secure, satisfying relationships support more adaptive patterns. Yet, despite strong conceptual foundations and consistent observational evidence, the field lacks a questionnaire that captures how individuals themselves experience these processes. The present work addresses this gap by developing and validating the Emotional Coregulation Scale, designed to assess the subjective experience of contagion and counter-regulation within close relationships.

2 Methods

2.1 Item Generation

The item pool was developed to operationalize Butler's theory of emotional coregulation at the level of subjective experience. Whereas previous studies have primarily examined coregulation through physiological synchrony, affective convergence, and behavioral coordination, no existing instrument captures how these processes are experienced by the individuals involved [Helm et al., 2014, Bornstein and Esposito, 2023, Zhou et al., 2024, Saxbe and Repetti, 2010, Schoebi, 2008]. The goal of this study was therefore to create a self-report scale assessing the two theoretically distinct components of emotional coregulation: *emotional contagion* (the sharing of affective states between partners) and *counter-regulation* (the buffering or balancing of one partner's emotions by the other).

Items were generated to represent both components of coregulation across positive and negative emotional states. This design was informed by theory and prior empirical findings suggesting that contagion is likely to occur for emotions of any valence, whereas counter-regulation emerges particularly when emotions are sufficiently intense, including high-arousal positive states such as excitement. With coregulation being a morphostatic process, the aim is not to maximize positive emotion or minimize negative emotion, but rather to maintain stability around a sustainable midpoint. Thus, items were written to reflect the regulation of both positive and negative emotions, with a focus on high-arousal positive emotions that are more likely to be subject to counter-regulation (e.g., excitement). All items were answered on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = "strongly disagree," 2 = "disagree," 3 = "neutral," 4 = "agree," 5 = "strongly agree").

To ensure applicability across relationship contexts, items were phrased such that the placeholder “X” could be replaced by the target person chosen by each participant (romantic partner, close friend, or family member). This design allows the scale to flexibly capture coregulation patterns across a range of close relationships, consistent with theory that these processes are not unique to romantic dyads.

Following initial drafting, the pool of items was reviewed by an expert in emotion regulation (co-author SK) for clarity, face validity, and coverage of the constructs. Feedback from Round 1 analyses, including evidence of redundancy and low-performing items, informed the refinement of the scales before Round 2. After each round, suggested edits were incorporated based on statistical results and expert input to maximize theoretical fit and psychometric quality.

2.2 Participants and Study Design

Two independent online samples were recruited through Prolific and completed the survey via Qualtrics. Eligibility criteria were age 18 or older and fluent English. Participants were compensated at a rate of £10 per hour. To ensure data quality, we included two attention-check questions, as well as automated bot detection and response quality checks (e.g. flagging straight-line responses) through Qualtrics. Participants who failed one or more of these checks were excluded. Round 1 had 127 participants, of whom **120** remained after exclusions. Round 2 had 121 participants, of whom **119** remained after exclusions. The two rounds functioned as separate stages of a validation study: Round 1 tested the initial item pool, and Round 2 re-tested a refined version of the scale in a new sample.

In Round 1, participants had a mean age of 28.3 years ($SD = 5.6$, range = 18–42), and 59% resided in the United Kingdom, 34% in the United States, and the remainder in other countries. In Round 2, the mean age was 30.6 years ($SD = 6.7$, range = 18–49), with 59% in the United Kingdom, 33% in the United States, and the remainder in other countries. Across both rounds, the majority self-identified as White (71–76%), with smaller proportions identifying as Black (17–19%) or Asian (5–7%). Samples were balanced in gender, with roughly equal numbers of men and women in both rounds. In both rounds, most participants identified a romantic partner as their closest relationship (the target for the coregulation questionnaire), with smaller proportions selecting a close friend or family member (see Table 1 for details).

Table 1: Demographic and Relationship Characteristics of Participants in Round 1 ($n = 120$) and Round 2 ($n = 119$).

	Round 1	Round 2
Age (years)		
Mean (SD)	28.3 (5.6)	30.6 (6.7)
Range	18–42	18–49
Gender		
Female	42%	41%
Male	58%	59%
Ethnicity		
White	71%	76%
Black	19%	17%
Asian	7%	5%
Mixed/Other	3%	2%
Country of residence		
United Kingdom	59%	59%
United States	34%	33%
Other	7%	8%
Relationship type		
Romantic partner	87%	71%
Close friend	11%	18%
Family member	12%	11%

Note. Relationship type is based on participants’ self-reported relationship type with the person they felt closest to. Participants were instructed to answer the coregulation scale questions with this person in mind.

2.3 Procedure

After providing informed consent, participants selected a close relationship target (romantic partner, friend, or family member). All questionnaire items were worded to reference this chosen target, ensuring that responses reflected a

specific relationship context. The survey included the new Emotional Coregulation Scale items along with other measures used for validation.

2.4 Analysis

Analyses were conducted in R using the packages `psych`, `dplyr`, `lavaan`, and `semTools`. We examined item distributions, corrected item–total correlations (CITR), and internal consistency using Cronbach’s α with 95% confidence intervals, as well as α if an item was deleted to evaluate each item’s contribution to the overall scale.

Confirmatory factor analyses (CFA) were conducted separately for emotional contagion and counter-regulation to test whether each subscale was adequately represented by a single-factor structure. CFAs were estimated with maximum likelihood, and model respecification was guided by modification indices in conjunction with theoretical considerations.

Discriminant validity was assessed for the final item pool by fitting models with all items from both subscales combined, comparing a one-factor solution (all items loading on a single factor) with a two-factor solution (items loading on contagion and counter-regulation factors separately). In addition, the heterotrait–monotrait ratio (HTMT) was calculated as a complementary analysis, because it has been recommended as a more sensitive test of discriminant validity than traditional CFA criteria [Ab Hamid et al., 2017, Henseler et al., 2015]. This allowed us to test whether contagion and counter-regulation are empirically distinguishable as related but separable constructs. Model fit was evaluated using the chi-square test of model fit (χ^2), the Comparative Fit Index (CFI), the Tucker–Lewis Index (TLI), the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA, with 90% confidence interval), and the Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR).

2.5 Criteria for Interpretation

Following standard recommendations, we considered Cronbach’s α values above .70 as indicating acceptable internal consistency [Nunnally and Bernstein, 1994]. For confirmatory factor analyses, we followed the guidelines of Hu and Bentler [1999] and Kline [2016], interpreting CFI and TLI values $\geq .95$ as indicating good fit, RMSEA values $\leq .08$ as indicating acceptable fit, and SRMR values $\leq .08$ as indicating good fit. In addition to strictly looking at these cutoffs, we interpreted indices taken together as a whole with emphasis on retaining the theoretical coherence of the constructs.

3 Results

The validation proceeded in two independent rounds. Round 1 provided the initial test of the item pool, while Round 2 evaluated the revised scales after item removal and rewording. Results for each round are reported separately, followed by a summary of discriminant validity across both.

3.1 Round 1: Initial Item Pool

In Round 1, internal consistency for the emotional contagion subscale was acceptable ($\alpha = .79$, 95% CI [.71, .84]). Values above .70 are generally considered acceptable for early-stage research [Nunnally and Bernstein, 1994], indicating that the six items captured a coherent construct. Item-total correlations suggested that most items contributed well, although the anger-related item (“*When I feel angry, X joins me in my anger*”) showed the weakest association ($r_{drop} = .28$), meaning this item was not as strongly aligned with the rest of the scale. The two general emotional contagion items (“*Interacting with X makes me feel like we are emotionally on the same wavelength*” and “*The way my partner responds to my emotions makes me feel like we are sharing a similar emotion*”) were highly correlated, suggesting redundancy and possible overlap in content.

Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) supported a one-factor structure for emotional contagion ($\chi^2(9) = 12.21$, $p = .20$, CFI = .98, TLI = .97, RMSEA = .06, SRMR = .04). According to conventional guidelines, CFI and TLI values above .95 indicate excellent fit, RMSEA values below .08 indicate acceptable fit, and SRMR values below .08 indicate good fit [Hu and Bentler, 1999, Kline, 2016]. Taken together, these results show that the one-factor model closely matched the data. Standardized loadings were strong for most items ($> .65$), but weaker for the anger item (.40) and one excitement item (.55), meaning these items showed weaker alignment with the other items in the scale.

For counter-regulation, internal consistency was good ($\alpha = .80$, 95% CI [.74, .85]), again exceeding the conventional .70 threshold for acceptable reliability. Most items contributed positively, though the item “*When I feel excited, X helps me stay level-headed*” showed the lowest contribution ($r_{drop} = .31$), suggesting it less consistent with the other items. CFA supported a one-factor model ($\chi^2(9) = 14.37$, $p = .11$, CFI = .97, TLI = .94, RMSEA = .07, SRMR = .05). These values indicate that the model fit the data well, with RMSEA and SRMR values suggesting close correspondence

between the observed and predicted relationships. Items reflecting sadness regulation and general soothing loaded most strongly, suggesting that these were the clearest indicators of counter-regulation.

Table 2: Factor loadings and reliability statistics for emotional contagion and counter-regulation items in Round 1 ($N = 120$).

Item	SL	CITR	α -drop
Emotional Contagion			
1. X mirrors my emotional state.	.81	.75	.71
2. When I feel angry, X joins me in my anger.	.40	.28	.82
3. When I feel sad, X shares my sadness.	.68	.58	.75
4. When I feel excited, X talks to me in a more excited manner.	.55	.48	.78
5. Interacting with X makes me feel like we are emotionally on the same wavelength.	.72	.56	.75
6. The way X responds to my emotions makes me feel like we are sharing a similar emotion.	.74	.61	.74
<i>Overall scale: $\alpha = .79$, 95% CI [.71, .84]</i>			
Counter-Regulation			
1. Interacting with X reduces the intensity of my emotions.	.59	.47	.78
2. When I feel angry, X responds in a calm and soothing way.	.61	.44	.79
3. When I feel sad, X tries to cheer me up.	.66	.55	.77
4. When I feel excited, X helps me stay level-headed.	.42	.31	.81
5. Interacting with X helps me to gain more control over my emotions.	.83	.71	.76
6. The way X responds to me helps me overcome any feelings of emotional distress.	.79	.68	.76
<i>Overall scale: $\alpha = .80$, 95% CI [.74, .85]</i>			

Note. SL = standardized factor loading from confirmatory factor analysis. CITR = corrected item–total correlation. α -drop = Cronbach’s alpha if the item were removed.

Based on these findings, two adjustments were made before Round 2. First, the emotional contagion item “*The way X responds to my emotions makes me feel like we are sharing a similar emotion*” and the counter-regulation item “*Interacting with X reduces the intensity of my emotions*” were removed due to redundancy. Second, anger-related items were rephrased to refer to “annoyance” rather than “anger,” as anger may be less frequent in everyday supportive interactions between close partners and had shown weak alignment with the construct. Finally, the excitement regulation item was retained despite weaker performance, as it captures an important theoretical dimension of regulating strong positive emotions.

3.2 Round 2: Revised Item Pool

In Round 2, the revised five-item emotional contagion scale demonstrated acceptable internal consistency ($\alpha = .73$, 95% CI [.65, .81]). Values above .70 suggest that the items formed a reliable scale [Nunnally and Bernstein, 1994]. Most items showed moderate to strong corrected item–total correlations, though the annoyance item (“*When I feel annoyed, X also gets annoyed more easily*”) remained the weakest contributor ($r_{drop} = .32$), indicating that it was less consistent with the other emotional contagion items. CFA confirmed a good one-factor fit ($\chi^2(5) = 6.36, p = .27$, CFI = .99, TLI = .98, RMSEA = .05, SRMR = .04). These values reflect excellent model–data correspondence [Hu and Bentler, 1999], suggesting that the revised emotional contagion scale captured the construct well. Standardized loadings were strong for most items (.65–.85), while the annoyance item remained lower (.35), indicating weaker but still meaningful representation of the construct.

The five-item counter-regulation subscale also showed good reliability ($\alpha = .77$, 95% CI [.69, .83]), comfortably above the .70 threshold for acceptable internal consistency [Nunnally and Bernstein, 1994]. Items addressing sadness regulation and general soothing (“*The way X responds to me helps me overcome feelings of emotional distress*”) loaded most strongly, indicating that they were the clearest indicators of the construct. The excitement regulation item (“*When I feel excited, X helps me stay level-headed*”) was again the weakest ($r_{drop} = .31$), showing weaker alignment with the other items. CFA supported a one-factor solution with acceptable fit ($\chi^2(5) = 10.40, p = .07$, CFI = .97, TLI = .94, RMSEA = .10, SRMR = .05). While the RMSEA was slightly above the preferred .08 cutoff, the other indices indicated good fit overall [Hu and Bentler, 1999], suggesting that the counter-regulation scale provides a coherent and valid measurement of the construct.

Table 3: Factor loadings and reliability statistics for emotional contagion and counter-regulation items in Round 2 ($N = 119$).

Item	SL	CITR	α -drop
Emotional Contagion			
1. X mirrors my emotional state.	.85	.74	.71
2. When I feel annoyed, X also gets annoyed more easily.	.35	.32	.76
3. When I feel sad, X shares my sadness.	.66	.58	.73
4. When I feel excited, X talks to me in a more excited manner.	.47	.48	.74
5. When I'm with X, they are emotionally on the same wavelength with me.	.76	.56	.73
<i>Overall scale: $\alpha = .73$, 95% CI [.65, .81]</i>			
Counter-Regulation			
1. When I feel annoyed, X responds in a calm and soothing way.	.54	.44	.76
2. When I feel sad, X tries to cheer me up.	.63	.55	.75
3. When I feel excited, X helps me stay level-headed.	.38	.31	.78
4. X helps me gain more control over my emotions.	.88	.71	.74
5. The way X responds to me helps me overcome feelings of emotional distress.	.83	.68	.74
<i>Overall scale: $\alpha = .77$, 95% CI [.69, .83]</i>			

Note. SL = standardized factor loading from confirmatory factor analysis. CITR = corrected item–total correlation. α -drop = Cronbach's alpha if the item were removed.

3.3 Discriminant Validity

Discriminant validity was evaluated only in Round 2, as this reflected the finalized scale after item refinement and therefore provided the most meaningful test of the distinctiveness of the two constructs. A two-factor model specifying emotional contagion and counter-regulation as separate latent variables was compared against a one-factor model in which all items loaded on a single factor. The two-factor solution fit the data substantially better ($\chi^2(34) = 85.30, p < .001, CFI = .87, TLI = .83, RMSEA = .11, SRMR = .11$) than the one-factor alternative ($\chi^2(35) = 153.50, p < .001, CFI = .71, TLI = .63, RMSEA = .17, SRMR = .12, \Delta\chi^2(1) = 68.20, p < .001$). This result suggests that emotional contagion and counter-regulation are better represented as two distinct but correlated factors rather than as a single construct. The latent correlation between the two factors was moderate ($r = .57$).

To further confirm discriminant validity, heterotrait–monotrait ratio (HTMT) analysis was conducted, as this index may be more sensitive than traditional CFA criteria [Henseler et al., 2015]. The HTMT value was 0.703, below the conventional .85 cutoff, supporting that emotional contagion and counter-regulation are related but separable dimensions.

Taken together, these results suggest that emotional contagion and counter-regulation are distinct yet moderately correlated processes. Conceptually, this could mean that couples who share affective states are also more likely to help regulate each other's emotions when they become too intense, as shared emotion may provide a foundation for effective counter-regulation. At the same time, each process plays a unique role, consistent with the view that both are subprocesses within the broader phenomenon of emotional coregulation.

3.4 Summary of Findings

Overall, the two rounds of validation provided consistent evidence that emotional contagion and counter-regulation can be measured reliably as two subcomponents of emotional coregulation. In Round 1, both subscales showed acceptable to good reliability, but several items demonstrated redundancy or weak fit, particularly anger-related and broad emotional contagion items.

After refinement, the Round 2 questionnaire demonstrated good reliability, with overall construct alphas in the .73–.77 range, meeting conventional psychometric standards. CFA models showed good to excellent fit, with SRMR values consistently well below .08, indicating close reproduction of the observed correlations. Although a few items remained weaker, they were retained to preserve theoretical coverage of the construct. Discriminant validity tests confirmed that emotional contagion and counter-regulation are related but distinct processes.

As a whole, these findings support the Emotional Coregulation Scale as a reliable and valid measure of the subjective experience of emotional contagion and counter-regulation in close relationships. The revisions from Round 1 to

Round 2 improved model fit and reduced redundancy, resulting in two subscales that are psychometrically sound while maintaining coverage of both positive and negative emotions.

Table 4: Summary of reliability and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) fit indices for emotional contagion and counter-regulation across Round 1 ($N = 120$) and Round 2 ($N = 119$).

Scale	Round	α (95% CI)	χ^2 (df)	CFI	TLI	RMSEA [90% CI]	SRMR
Emotional Contagion	1	.79 [.71, .84]	12.21 (9), $p = .20$.98	.97	.06 [.00, .12]	.04
	2	.73 [.65, .81]	6.36 (5), $p = .27$.99	.98	.05 [.00, .15]	.04
Counter-Regulation	1	.80 [.74, .85]	14.37 (9), $p = .11$.97	.94	.07 [.00, .13]	.05
	2	.77 [.69, .83]	10.40 (5), $p = .07$.97	.94	.10 [.00, .18]	.05

Note. α = Cronbach’s alpha; CI = confidence interval; χ^2 = chi-square goodness-of-fit test; df = degrees of freedom; CFI = comparative fit index; TLI = Tucker–Lewis index; RMSEA = root mean square error of approximation; SRMR = standardized root mean square residual.

4 Discussion

This study set out to develop and validate the Emotional Coregulation Questionnaire, designed to capture two subprocesses of interpersonal emotional dynamics: emotional contagion (sharing of affect) and counter-regulation (balancing of affect). Across two rounds of online data collection, the questionnaire demonstrated acceptable-to-good internal consistency and a coherent factorial structure, supporting its use as a brief self-report tool for assessing how individuals experience coregulation within close relationships.

Confirmatory factor analyses supported single-factor solutions for both contagion and counter-regulation in each round, with generally strong item loadings. Although a few items showed weaker contributions—most notably those involving anger or annoyance—these results highlight the challenge of capturing less frequent or socially complex emotions in close relationships. Their performance suggests that affective states such as anger may operate differently from sadness or excitement in interpersonal regulation, a nuance that future work should explore further.

Discriminant validity analyses indicated that contagion and counter-regulation are related but distinct dimensions. The two-factor model fit the data significantly better than a one-factor alternative, and the HTMT ratio confirmed their separability. This pattern is theoretically consistent with the idea that sharing emotions and buffering them are complementary subprocesses of emotional coregulation: couples who align in affect may also be better positioned to help modulate each other’s emotions when they become overwhelming. Yet each process fulfills a distinct role, with contagion facilitating emotional connection and counter-regulation supporting balance and stability.

At the same time, several limitations temper these conclusions. Both samples were convenience samples recruited via Prolific, and were demographically skewed toward English-speaking participants from the UK and US. Sample sizes, while adequate for initial validation, were modest, and missing data in earlier rounds reduced the number of cases available for some CFA models. Moreover, the study focused solely on internal structure and discriminant validity; other aspects of validation, such as convergent and divergent validity with existing measures, test–retest reliability, and measurement invariance across demographic groups, remain untested. Without these additional steps, the questionnaire should be considered a promising tool still in early stages of validation.

Another limitation is the absence of external behavioral or physiological data. Emotional coregulation is a dynamic interpersonal process, often measured through emotional contagion in physiology or observed interaction patterns. While self-report captures subjective experience, it may not fully align with objective indicators. Linking questionnaire scores to behavioral or physiological measures would be an important next step for establishing construct validity and deepening understanding of how subjective and objective coregulation relate.

Despite these limitations, the present study provides an important foundation. The Emotional Coregulation Questionnaire is brief, theory-driven, and psychometrically supported, and thus offers a tool for assessing how individuals perceive emotional processes in their closest relationships. The instrument may prove useful in research on couple dynamics, friendship, and family relationships, as well as in applied settings such as clinical interventions focused on emotion regulation within dyads.

5 Conclusion

Taken together, the findings indicate that emotional contagion and counter-regulation are distinct but interconnected subprocesses of emotional coregulation. The Emotional Coregulation Scale presented in this paper provides the first

self-report instrument to measure these experiences directly, creating opportunities for researchers and practitioners to assess how close partners influence each other's emotional states. While further validation in larger and more diverse samples is needed, the present study demonstrates the feasibility of capturing subjective experiences of emotional coregulation in a concise and reliable way.

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